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Influence of the addition of thermoplastic healing agent to epoxy resin

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Motivation

- Composite materials
 - ✓ Exposure to environmental factors and mechanical loading may lead to the formation of microcracks
 - *Microcracks difficult to detect*
 - *Costly repairs / failure*

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Self-healing materials

- Alternative to conventional repair methods to heal microcracks in the structure
 - ✓ Extension of service life
 - ✓ Reduction of maintenance cycles
 - ✓ Increase reliability

- Repair associated to restoration of properties:

Bio-inspired

$$\text{Healing efficiency} = \frac{\text{Property value}_{\text{healed}}}{\text{Property value}_{\text{initial}}} \times 100$$

Self-healing in epoxy and epoxy composites

- Thermoplastic healing agents
 - ✓ Addition of thermoplastic particles to epoxy matrix
 - ✓ Heating during healing cycle allows increase in mobility of thermoplastic material and flow to damaged areas
 - ✓ Thermoplastic as a crack filler capable of re-bonding fracture surfaces.

D. Y. Wu et al, Prog. Polym. Sci. 33 (2008) 479–522

Self-healing in epoxy and epoxy composites

MEURE; WU; FURMAN, 2009:

- Addition of 15 wt.% of thermoplastic particles (polyethylene-co-methacrylic acid) (EMAA) to epoxy resin
 - ✓ Decrease in modulus + increase in fracture strength
 - ✓ Recovery = 85% (TDCB) and 100% (SENB)

healed SENB showing the fracture plane

(I) epoxy resin, (II) an EMAA particle and (III) crack

EMAA particle healing and formation of an adhesive EMAA layer between adjacent epoxy fracture surfaces

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Fatigue behavior of self-healing glass fiber/epoxy composites with addition of poly (ethylene-co-methacrylic acid) (EMAA)

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Fatigue behaviour and self-healing

- Composites with 2 wt% and 5 wt% of EMAA were manufactured by resin infusion using glass fibers impregnated with EMAA
- Healing efficiency: number of cycles to failure of specimens subjected to cyclic loading
- No significant effect on glass transition temperature, tensile strength or modulus of elasticity

Fatigue behaviour and self-healing

- 5 wt% of EMAA: reduction of the fatigue life
- 2 wt% of EMAA: slight increase in life
- greatest number of cycles to failure of composites: with 2 wt% of EMAA
- greatest healing efficiency: healing cycle after 10^3 loading cycles, as compared to 10^4 loading cycles: healing can be more efficient if activated in early stages of damage.

Table 3. Average healing efficiency of unmodified and modified composites.

Sample	η (%)	
	10^3	10^4
Unmodified composites	105.9	31.2
E2% composites	102.1	27.4
E5% composites	199.6	37.7

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Effects of particle size and particle concentration of poly (ethylene-co-methacrylic acid) on properties of epoxy resin

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Effects of particles in epoxy

- addition of EMAA: reduction in tensile strength and modulus of elasticity of epoxy resin

- EMAA particle dispersion along the length of samples was not homogenous: X-CT studies

Effects of particles in epoxy

- lower EMAA concentration with smaller particle sizes may be optimal condition, considering the maintenance of base tensile properties of epoxy and homogeneity in particle distribution
- trade-off between healing efficiency and the reduction of mechanical properties must be considered and adjusted by the selection of particle concentration and particle size of the healing agent

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Paper of the month of August: Material

Effects of particle size and particle concentration of poly (ethylene-co-methacrylic acid) on properties of epoxy resin

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> Effects of particle size and particle concentration of poly (ethylene-co-methacrylic acid) on properties of epoxy resin

NASCIMENTO, ALLANA ; TRAPPE, VOLKER ; PAVASARYTE, LINA ; MELO, JOSÉ ; BARBOSA, ana paula cysne .
Effects of particle size and particle concentration of poly (ethylene-co-methacrylic acid) on properties of epoxy resin.
JOURNAL OF APPLIED POLYMER SCIENCE

Preliminary results on crack propagation

- Crack propagation in SET samples investigated for neat epoxy and epoxy with 5 wt.% of thermoplastic (EMAA) particles, with 2 different particle sizes
- Preliminary results indicate that cracks seems to propagate faster for neat epoxy than for epoxy modified with thermoplastic material

Fracture surface of neat epoxy SET sample

Conclusions and outlook

- Self-healing with thermoplastic particles as alternative to heal material and extend service life
- Healing can be more efficient if activated in early stages of damage
- Trade-off between healing efficiency and the reduction of mechanical properties must be considered
- Ongoing studies on crack propagation of epoxy with and without thermoplastic particles

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Thank you!
Obrigada!